

Investigating the impact of the new European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 on the seismic design and safety control of industrial facilities

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Abstract: The seismic performance and safety of major European industrial facilities has a global interest for Europe, its citizens and economy. A potential major disaster at an industrial site could affect several countries, probably far beyond the country where it is located. However, the seismic design and safety assessment of these facilities is practically based on national, often outdated seismic hazard assessment studies, due to many reasons, including the absence of a reliable, commonly developed seismic hazard model for whole Europe. This important gap is no more existing, as the 2020 European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 was released in December 2021. In this paper we investigate the expected impact of the adoption of ESHM20 on the seismic demand for industrial facilities, through the comparison of the ESHM20 probabilistic hazard at the sites where industrial facilities are located with the respective national and European regulations. The goal of this preliminary work in the framework of Working Group 13 of the European Association for Earthquake Engineering (EAEE), is to identify potential inadequacies in the design and safety control of existing industrial facilities and to highlight the expected impact of the adoption of the new European Seismic Hazard Model on the design of new industrial facilities and the safety assessment of existing ones.

Keywords: ESHM20, industrial facilities; seismic hazard; seismic design; safety control

1. Introduction

The seismic performance and safety of major European industrial facilities has a global interest for Europe, its citizens and economy. A potential major disaster at an industrial site could affect several countries, probably far beyond the country where it is located. However, the seismic design and safety assessment of these facilities is practically based on national, often outdated seismic hazard assessment studies, due to many reasons, including the absence of a reliable, commonly developed and accepted seismic hazard model for whole Europe. This important gap is no more existing, as the 2020 European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021) was released in December 2021. It is also important that the main results of this new updated European Model have been officially adopted as reference for the seismic hazard assessment in the upcoming revision of Eurocode 8. The adoption of ESHM20 by Eurocode 8 is expected to have a significant impact on the seismic demand for industrial facilities, and it was therefore considered as crucial by the Working Group 13 of the European Association for Earthquake Engineering (EAEE) to investigate this impact at the European sites where major industrial facilities are located. In the framework of this ongoing work, we present in this paper the conceptual basis of the comparison between ESHM20 output and national / European codes and regulations, as well as preliminary results for the sites where the major industrial facilities in Greece are located, focusing on the comparison between the ESHM20 probabilistic

hazard with the respective European regulations. The goal of this preliminary work is to identify potential inadequacies in the design and safety control of existing industrial facilities and to highlight the expected impact of the adoption of the new European Seismic Hazard Model on the design of new industrial facilities and the safety assessment of existing ones.

2. Conceptual basis

Typical production units in industrial facilities consist of the primary load-carrying structure and various process engineering components. In addition, supply structures such as free-standing tanks and silos are usually required for each plant to ensure the supply of material and product storage. Thus, design and construction rules are required for the primary structures, the secondary structures and the supply structures. Within the framework of these rules, interactions of primary and secondary structures must also be taken into account. So far, in most of the national codes in European countries importance factors are applied in seismic design to sufficiently take into account the higher risk potential of the plant compared to conventional building structures. However, the importance factors given in the current version of Eurocode 8-1 (CEN, 2004) cannot be applied to industrial facilities because they refer solely to standard buildings with their corresponding damage potential. Furthermore, the importance factors given in Eurocode 8-4 (CEN, 2004) are limited to silos, tanks and pipelines. Suitable importance factors for industrial facilities should consider the impact on people, health and safety, the impact on the environment and the impact due to failure of lifeline functionalities within the plants. Such a holistic approach can presently neither be found in national nor in international standards. A reasonable approach is given in the VCI Guidelines “The seismic load case in plant construction” (VCI-Leitfaden, 2022a;b) which complements the rules of Eurocode 8 for industrial facilities. Similar guidelines were developed in France “Guide méthodologique pour la conception, l’installation et le diagnostic des équipements en zone sismique” (AFPS, 2011). The values of the importance factors given in these documents were agreed upon on the basis of interdisciplinary expertise and have been checked against international standards.

However, the use of importance factors is only a simple linear scaling of response spectra defined in standards. Such a linear scaling can only constitute a rough approximation, since for different return periods both spectral shapes and the boundaries of seismic zones are subject to change. It is certainly more meaningful to choose a higher return period instead of importance factors and to determine the corresponding spectrum with updated probabilistic seismic hazard maps, which will be available in Europe thanks to the new European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021). The new maps for different return periods avoid the errors related to simple scaling of the code spectra and provide a reliable basis for performance-based design, that allows an individually tailored design of facilities to minimize damage and costs due to loss of functionality for different exceedance probabilities. Furthermore, their introduction will correct the problem with non-seismic zones in seismic codes, which imply that there will be no seismic action, no matter how high the adopted importance factor may be, while it is clear that for higher return periods parts of non-seismic zones may indeed acquire some degree of seismic hazard. New hazard maps based on ESHM20 will also provide an excellent basis for the assessment of existing facilities, which were often build using outdated hazard maps or without any consideration of seismic actions. The safety verification of existing facilities requires the correct definition of the seismic input using ESHM20 to allow a fully

utilization of the load-bearing reserves by means of nonlinear analysis (Meskouris et al., 2019).

However, ESHM20 can also be integrated in modern systems for the protection and safety control of industrial facilities. These new and innovative systems consist of four basic components: (i) the seismic sensor network, (ii) the local monitoring systems within the facility, (iii) the communication infrastructure and (iv) the integration of the sensor data in digital models of the monitored facility. ESHM20 can support the optimal arrangement of the regional seismic network in the regarded area with stochastic simulations of scenario earthquakes. Fundamental element of the novel systems is the automated interaction of smart sensors or sensor systems, which are capable not only to record motions or strains, but also to process the recordings decentral and to forward the results of the assessment. Guidelines for the seismic risk assessment of major-hazard industrial plants and its mitigation through smart sensors were developed in Italy (Ciucci et al., 2019). In Germany the novel early warning and rapid response system for earthquake events in the Lower Rhine region “ROBUST” is under development with German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) and applied to a chemical production unit close to Cologne (Butenweg, 2021). Further possible applications were developed in the project SYNER-G (Pitilakis et al, 2016) and in Greece for school buildings (Pitilakis et al., 2022). ESHM20 will also allow the planning and installation of systems regardless of national borders and contribute to the harmonisation process of seismic risk assessment of facilities in Europe.

3. Seismic demand for industrial facilities in the Eurocodes

In the current version of Eurocode 8 (CEN 2004), the European Standard for the seismic design of structures, the design of industrial facilities is partially covered by Part 4, limited to silos, tanks and pipelines, providing recommended values for importance factors, γ_i , for four importance classes I-IV and suggesting that the National Annexes should provide more precise values which may differentiate for the various seismic zones of the country. The recommended values range from 0.8 for importance class I (associated with low risk for loss of life and negligible risk for the social and economic consequences of failures) up to 1.6 for class IV (for situations with exceptional risk of life and extreme economic and social consequences of failure). The general part for the definition of seismic actions (Eurocode 8 Part 1) further suggests that the importance factors may be defined for a return period considered as more appropriate for the design of a specific structure T_L , when the seismic hazard is available for a different reference return period T_{LR} (usually 475 years), as $(T_{LR}/T_L)^{-1/k}$, where k is an exponent depending on seismicity of the order of 3.

In the ongoing revision of Eurocode 8, importance factors will be replaced by performance factors $\gamma_{LS,CC}$, based on the adopted Limit State (LS) and Consequence Class (CC), with values up to 1.8 for the Significant Damage (SD) limit state which is recommended for structures covered by Part 4 (Silos, tanks and pipelines, towers, masts and chimneys) (CEN, 2021a). Alternatively, the performance requirements may be achieved by appropriate return periods $T_{LS,CC}$, depending on the limit states and consequence class of the structure and its secondary elements.

4. Brief description of ESHM20 and its output

In the last two decades, a lot of efforts have been made to improve the seismic hazard maps worldwide, adopting the results of probabilistic seismic hazard analyses and to harmonize seismic hazard maps over broader regions, e.g., at continental or even global level (GEM,

Silva et al., 2020). Regarding similar efforts at European level, in December 2021 the European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021) was released, developed within the EU funded project “Seismology and Earthquake Engineering Research Infrastructure Alliance for Europe” (SERA). This model, which is fully probabilistic, is essentially an update of the previous ESHM13 (Woessner et al., 2013), proposed in the framework of SHARE project (Giardini et al., 2013), and was built upon recently compiled and fully cross-border harmonized datasets (i.e., earthquake catalogues, active faults, ground shaking recordings), information (tectonic and geological) and models (seismogenic sources, ground shaking). The source data, input models and output of ESHM20 are online available at the portal of the European Facilities for Earthquake Hazard and Risk (www.hazard.EFEHR.org), which will maintain and further develop the model in collaboration with the GEM Foundation and the European Plate Observing System (EPOS). Apart from the strictly scientific objectives of ESHM20, including the development of the actual updated and harmonized model and the support of the development of the European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20, Crowley et al., 2021), one of the main objectives was to interact with CEN/TC250/SC8, i.e., the subcommittee of national experts that is responsible for the development of Eurocode 8 within the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), as well as with key experts at national level, to ensure the correct information and timely implementation of the ESHM20, and extend the output to serve additional engineering requirements as part of the ongoing update and revision of Eurocode 8.

The results of ESHM20 are given for a computational grid with 97920 points, equally spaced at 0.1 to 0.1 degrees, and include hazard maps for specified intensity measure types (PGA, spectra acceleration with 5% damping at predominant periods in the range of 0.05s to 5s) and five mean return periods (i.e. 50, 475, 975, 2500 and 5000 years), hazard curves at every computational site, depicting the mean, median (50th) and four quantiles (5th, 16th, 84th and 95th) for all intensity measure types and Uniform Hazard Spectra for the mean, median and four quantiles and the five return periods. In addition to the above, and as a result of the interaction of ESHM20 with CEN/TC250/SC8, two additional hazard maps were developed for the two seismic hazard parameters adopted by the new under revision Eurocode 8 - Part1 (CEN, 2021b), $S_{\alpha,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$ for rock conditions, which will be included in an Annex of the revised Eurocode 8, as an “acceptable representation of the seismic hazard in Europe for the return period of 475 years”.

5. Application to industrial sites in Greece

The adoption of the new seismic hazard model ESHM20 for the seismic demand of industrial facilities is expected to have a significant impact on the design of new industrial facilities and the safety assessment of existing ones. It was therefore considered crucial by the Working Group 13 of the European Association for Earthquake Engineering (EAEE) to investigate this impact at the European sites where major industrial facilities are located (Fig. 1 presents a map of these locations). The main criteria of selection were the type of the facility and the size and the amount of material handling. Important industrial facilities located in earthquake-prone areas were also included in this study. A part of this work is presented in this paper, focusing on selected sites located in Greece (Fig. 2) and the comparisons between the ESHM20 probabilistic hazard with the one obtained from the current and revised EC8, as well as the Greek seismic code EAK 2000, taking also into account the effect of the importance factors and the site conditions.

Fig. 1 – Locations of the sites in Europe with important industrial facilities

Fig. 2 – Locations of major industrial sites in Greece

Some representative examples of the above-mentioned comparisons are given in Figures 3-6 for Aspropyrgos refinery, the largest refinery station in Greece (ID=1 in Figure 2). More specifically, in Figures 3 and 4 we compare the horizontal elastic response spectra for a mean return period of 475 years, i.e. assuming that they are ordinary structures and thus without adopting any importance factors, based on the Greek seismic code EAK 2000, the current Eurocode 8 (CEN, 2004) and the proposed review of Eurocode 8 (CEN, 2021b) for rock site conditions (Figure 3) and taking into account the local site conditions at the site of Aspropyrgos refinery (soil class B based on EAK, soil class B based on current EC8 and soil class B or C based on the revised EC8) (Figure 4). We should highlight the important discrepancies in terms of definition of site classes and amplification factors between the two version of Eurocode 8, the detailed description of which is beyond the scope of this paper. In summary, in the new version of Eurocode 8, the depth to seismic bedrock is considered as an additional parameter for the definition of the site classes, while the amplification factors, provided both in the form of analytical or default values, depending on the level of knowledge of V_{s30} and depth to seismic bedrock H_{800} , are intensity dependent in an effort to take into account nonlinear site response. Soil class B based on the current EC8 refers to stiff soils (dense sand, gravel or very stiff clay) with at least several tens of meters in thickness, while soil classes B and C based on the revised EC8 refer to intermediate depth class of stiff soils and soils of medium stiffness respectively. We observe that the constant acceleration branch (plateau) in both the current EC8 and EAK spectra for rock site conditions extends up to much higher spectral periods compared

to the revised EC8, which follows closely the ESHM20 UHS, based on which it has been derived (Figure 3). Regarding the effect of local site conditions, the plateau for EAK corresponds to lower acceleration, as no soil amplification factor is included in EAK, while the significant discrepancies between the spectra obtained with the analytical or the default amplification factors in the revised EC8 are also evident (Figure 4).

Fig. 3 – Horizontal elastic response spectra for a return period of 475 years calculated for the Aspropyrgos Refinery site for rock site conditions, based on EAK, the current Eurocode 8 and the review of Eurocode 8 and ESHM20 UHS.

Fig. 4 – Horizontal elastic response spectra for a return period of 475 years calculated for the Aspropyrgos Refinery site considering local site conditions, based on EAK (soil class B), the current Eurocode 8 (soil class B) and the review of Eurocode 8 (soil class B or C).

In Figure 5 we compare the horizontal elastic response spectra for rock site conditions based on the Greek seismic coded (EAK), the current Eurocode 8 and the proposed revised Eurocode 8 considering importance or performance factors that roughly correspond to a mean return period of 2500 years, which is commonly used in the seismic design of such critical facilities. For EAK we adopted an importance factor of 1.3, the highest one prescribed by the Greek code, for the current version of EC8 we considered (a) an

importance factor γ_i equal to 1.6 (importance class IV) and, alternatively (b) an importance factor γ_i equal to 1.74 to convert the design acceleration with a return period of 475 years to a return period of 2500 years. For the revised version of Eurocode 8 we used a performance factor $\gamma_{LS,CC}=1.8$ (Consequence Class CC3-b and Significant Damage (SD) limit state), which corresponds to a return period of 2500 years (CEN, 2021a) as multiplication factor to the reference spectral parameters $S_{\alpha,ref}$ and $S_{\beta,ref}$, which were derived from ESHM20 using the closest to the site grid point. The ESHM20 Uniform Hazard Spectrum (UHS) for a return period of 2500 years is also included in the figure. We observe that the spectral acceleration at the plateau of the spectrum based on the revised EC8 is almost identical to the one of the current EC8 with γ_i equal to 1.74, however its width is much narrower, following closely the shape of the ESHM20 UHS on which $S_{\alpha,ref}$ and $S_{\beta,ref}$ have been based. Similar comparisons are presented in Figure 6, taking also into account the local site conditions at the site of Aspropyrgos refinery.

Fig. 5 – Horizontal elastic response spectra for a return period of 2500 years calculated for the Aspropyrgos Refinery site for rock site conditions, based on EAK, the current Eurocode 8 with an importance factor γ_i equal to 1.6 (green continuous line) or 1.7 (green dashed line), the review of Eurocode 8 with a performance factor equal to 1.8 (blue line) and ESHM20 UHS.

The adoption of the ESHM20 and the revised EC8 leads to up to 15% higher plateau values on the horizontal elastic response spectrum compared to the ones using the current EC8 and the proposed importance factor γ_i equal to 1.6 (importance class IV) (solid green line), the descending branch of which is almost identical to the one of the revised EC8 considering the soil class C and the proposed default values for the amplification factors. There is a remarkable difference between the spectral accelerations considering the revised EC8 and the analytical amplification factors, which may be adopted when the $v_{s,H}$ (in most cases equal to $V_{s,30}$) and the depth to bedrock H_{800} are available, both for soil class B and C (dashed and solid blue lines), and the respective accelerations using the default values (dashed and solid orange lines). The commonly used importance factor γ_i equal to 1.6 in the current EC8 leads to lower spectral acceleration at the plateau of the spectrum compared to the revised EC8. On the other hand, the adoption of the importance factor γ_i equal to 1.74 used to convert the design acceleration with a return period of 475 years to a

return period of 2500 years leads to a more conservative design spectrum. The Greek seismic code EAK underpredicts the elastic spectra in all cases.

Fig. 6 – Horizontal elastic response spectra for a return period of 2500 years calculated for the Aspropyrgos Refinery site considering local site conditions, based on the EAK (soil class B), the current Eurocode 8 (soil class B) with an importance factor γ_i equal to 1.6 (green continuous line) or 1.7 (green dashed line) and the review of Eurocode 8 (soil class B or C) with a performance factor equal to 1.8 using the default amplification factors (orange lines) or the analytical amplification factors (blue lines).

Fig. 7 – Ratios of maximum spectral accelerations for rock site conditions based on the revised EC8 using S_a and S_B from ESHM20 and a performance factor equal to 1.8, to the respective values obtained from the current EC8 using an importance factor equal to 1.6 (grey dots) or 1.74 (red triangles) for the major industrial sites in Greece shown in Figure 2.

The results obtained for all the 16 industrial sites in Greece (see Figure 2) are summarized in Figures 7 and 8, where we compare the ratios of the maximum spectral accelerations for 2500 years return period obtained from the revised and the current EC8 for rock site conditions (Figure 7) and considering site effects with the default site amplification factors where site condition are only approximately estimated (Figure 8). The ratios are in general greater than one, reaching values up to 2.2 depending on the adopted importance factor; moreover they are usually amplified when local site conditions are considered due to the

additional effect of the differences in site amplification between the current and the revised EC8. This practically means that the adoption of the revised EC8 along with ESHM20 leads to significantly higher spectral accelerations at the plateau of the spectrum compared to the current EC8 either considering the 1.6 or the 1.74 importance factors. The maximum accelerations of over half of the examined industrial sites in Greece increases over 50% using the revised EC8, which indicates that the potential adoption of ESHM20 in combination with the revised EC8 is expected to have a significant impact on the design of new industrial facilities and the risk assessment and safety control of existing ones.

Fig. 8 – Ratios of maximum spectral accelerations taking into account local site conditions based on the revised EC8 using S_a and S_β from ESHM20 and a performance factor equal to 1.8, to the respective values obtained from the current EC8 using an importance factor equal to 1.6 (grey dots) or 1.74 (red triangles) for the major industrial sites in Greece shown in Figure 2. For sites 1, 6 and 7 two different cases were considered for the site class based on the revised EC8 (soil classes B and C).

6. Conclusions

In this work we presented preliminary results on the potential impact of the adoption of ESHM20 and the ongoing revision of Eurocode 8 on the seismic demand for industrial facilities in Greece, focusing on comparisons between the elastic response spectra of the current EC8 and the revised EC8, taking into account also the differences in the importance factors and the consideration of site-effects. The maximum acceleration of over half of the examined industrial sites in Greece increases over 50% using the revised EC8 in combination with ESHM20, which indicates that the new seismic hazard model for Europe (ESHM20) combined with the revised EC8 is expected to have a significant impact on the design of new industrial facilities and the risk assessment and safety control of existing ones when compared to existing code prescriptions (at least for Greece). The goal of this preliminary work, which is ongoing within Working Group 13 of the European Association for Earthquake Engineering (EAEE), is to ultimately identify potential inadequacies in the design of new industrial facilities and the safety control of existing industrial facilities.

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